

BIO FERTILIZERS: A METHOD TO SUSTAIN MICROFLORA AND FERTILITY OF SOIL

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Abstract

Biofertilizers emerge as crucial components in sustainable agriculture, presenting viable alternatives to traditional chemical fertilizers. This detailed review discusses the complex nature of biofertilizers as a means of maintaining the soil microflora and fertility. The mechanisms behind their efficiency, such as nitrogen fixation, phosphorus solubilization and also potassium mobilization, are discussed to show how these actions increase the availability of nutrients in the soil. The interaction between the biofertilizers and plants results in symbiotic relationships, which contribute to the microbial diversity forming a dynamic soil biosphere. The ecological importance of the biofertilizers is emphasized, and the footprint associated with chemical fertilization is reduced. Challenges and constraints, including the shelf life and cost issues, are discussed providing suggestions that can be applied in the future, drawing on successful case studies. Case studies demonstrate successful implementations, lessons learned and also the connection between biofertilizers and the precision agriculture. The future perspectives section describes the dynamic nature of the biofertilizer research, highlighting the possibility of specialized formulations designed for particular crops and also agroecological conditions. The transformative approach to biofertilizer application optimization is highlighted as the integration with precision agriculture, in line with data-driven and also technology-intensive farming. As a call to action, the review recommends biofertilizers' usage more widely; farmers, policymakers and also researchers should work together. In order to promote wide acceptance, it is necessary to carry out the awareness programs for the farmers and also create supportive policies. The abstract ends by highlighting how we have a collective responsibility to fully utilize the great potential of biofertilizers towards sustainable agriculture, soil health and also food security at the global level.

Keywords: Biofertilizers, Sustainable Agriculture, Soil Microflora, Nutrient Cycling

Introduction**Historical Background**

The background of biofertilizers lies in the growing recognition of the critical role of microorganisms in soil health and fertility. Soil is a very complicated ecosystem that hosts an array of the microbial population which actively contributes to both the nutrient recycling and also plant growth promotion. The negative effects of intensive farming, like chemical fertilizers and environmental degradation on soil productivity, has further clarified the requirement of sustainable alternatives to improve the soil quality. Soil microorganisms, such as nitrogen-fixing bacteria, and also phosphate-solubilizing fungi are very critical in transforming plant essential nutrients into different forms that plants can readily absorb (Daniel et al., 2022; Mahanty et al. This natural process also strengthens the sustainability of agricultural systems by promoting the plant nutrition. But typical agricultural practices are very likely to disturb these microbial communities, which affects the levels of nutrient availability and also compromises soil fertility. These challenges have led to the emergence of biofertilizers as a very viable option. Biofertilizers are living microorganisms that, when applied to the soil or plant surfaces, increase the availability and uptake of nutrients by establishing symbiotic relationships with the plants or solubilizing the nutrient elements. This method is also very consistent with the principles of sustainable agriculture as it decreases the dependence on artificial fertilizers and promotes a more mutual relationship between the plants and their microbial environment. Sustainable agriculture is incomplete without the application of biofertilizers because this practice limits the need for chemical fertilizers and also improves soil fertility.

However, biofertilizers have their roots in the 19th century when Justus von Liebig discovered that the nitrogen was important for the plant development (Martins et al. 2022). Rhizobium was first developed as a biofertilizer in the early 1900s that was used to inoculate the leguminous crops. After that, various types of biofertilizers have emerged, including the nitrogen-fixing biofertilizers, phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizers, potassium mobilization biofertilizers and sulfur oxidation Bio fertilizers with PGPRs (Kumar et al 2022). These biofertilizers have the capacity to fix atmospheric nitrogen on solubilized phosphorus, mobilize potassium oxidate sulfur and produce plant growth-promoting substances. Biofertilizers are eco-friendly, economical to use and increase the fertility of soils resulting in better crop yield. The idea of

identifying biofertilizers as a functional and non-toxic form of fertilizer has become popular in the recent past (Mitter et al. 2017). The more the researchers get a better understanding of how microbes and plants relate to one another, biofertilizers have played significant roles in agricultural practices as they continuously aid in restoring soil fertility.

In a nutshell, the background of biofertilizers is built on addressing challenges such as diminishing soil fertility, environmental issues and sustainable practice under farming. The realization of the complex interrelationships between microorganisms and Soil health has led to biofertilizer formulation as a viable alternative to preserve soil refrigerators.

Soil fertility and its importance

Soil fertility is the foundation for agricultural productivity and ecosystem sustainability, nutritional value on plant development. It involves the capacity of the soil to supply essential nutrients in forms that are available for plant uptake and thereby facilitating optimal growth and development. Soil fertility further enhances its significance by directly influencing agriculture production and yield, food security, the environment sustainability. This has been observed in different studies, including the study Wolf et al. (2023), which found that soil fertility must be kept to adequately provide nutrients for plants. As a result, the soils exhibit diverse form of nutrients including nitrogen phosphorus and potassium in addition to micronutrients that are vital for plant development. However, regular harvesting of the crops and nutrient mining by them along with other environmental problems will lead to depletion these important elements in soil over a period.

This is one of the major factors that have been used in addressing nutrient deficiencies and enhance soil fertility. However, they play as an efficient and timely nutrient source which means better yield in combination with sustainability of global food production (Krasilnicov et al 2021). A major contemporary farming practice is the introduction of fertilizers, which help in increasing production and addressing growing global population. Furthermore, the importance of soil fertility is not only manifested in crop production. A good example is fertile soils that help in determining the quality of ecosystems because they cause a lot of biodiversity and many services for an ecosystem. In terms of the environmental issues, healthy soils contribute to the erosion and nutrient runoff; carbon sequestration by soil significantly guides strategies for mitigating global climate change (Telo et al 2023). However, it is important to

stress that the unmanaged use of chemical fertilizers may lead to several environmental hazards like soil erosion groundwater contamination and also greenhouse gasses emissions. This realisation has resulted into adoption of sustainable soil management approaches that emphasize on balanced fertilization, organic amendments and also include other alternative methods including biofertilizers which maintain the soil's fertility but also reduce their negative impact on environment. In fact, soil fertility regarded in relation to the modern use of fertilisers occupies a key position for practice regarding sustainable agriculture and food security as well as environmental preservation.

Deterioration of soil fertility and the requirement for sustainable solutions

The reduction of soil fertility has become an urgent issue worldwide due to the combination of intensive agricultural practices, environmental degradation and over dependent on chemical fertilizers. It has a very negative impact on the sustainable agriculture, food security and also on ecosystem stability. Many studies show the many numerous negative trends that indicate soil fertility impoverishment. For instance, in their work that was reported (Lal et al. 2015), the continuous farming without good soil management leads to nutrient loss, erosion and degradation of soils. The application of contemporary agriculture practices such as the use of monoculture and over-reliance on chemical inputs results in the loss of soil organic matter that destroys complex microorganisms interactions aggravating fertility issues. One of the principal reasons contributing to soil infertility is the excessive synthetic fertilizers use. While these fertilizers may boost the yield of the crops initially, they come with many downsides on a long run. The uncontrolled use of nitrogen, phosphorus along with potassium without proper focus on the other supplementary nutrients leads to an imbalance in their availability which impacts negatively on soil structure and also microbial diversity (Rashid et al., 2016). To counteract such threats, a growing understanding of the necessity for sustainable approaches leading to the preserving and protecting soil fertility is present. Therefore sustainability in soil management aims at increasing the health of all the soils with a minimum adverse impact on the environment. Some of the practices suggested to prevent fertility loss are conservation tillage, cover cropping as well as agro forestry (Lal et al. 2015).

Additionally, organic based farming practices and the integration of organic modifications are becoming indeed common. The organic-matter enhances soil structure, water retaining capacity and nutrient-cycling thereby creating an additional balanced and sustainable soil-ecosystem (Carceles et al. 2022). Also, there are various sustainable agriculture-practices such as use of the biofertilizers, crop-rotation which are helpful in restoring the fertility of soil through improved nitrogen-cycling and microbial diversity (Fasusi et al. 2021). Conclusively, the deterioration in soil-fertility poses substantial hazard to environmental sustainability and global agriculture. It is necessary to change the approach towards this problem by directioning on an ecological feature of soil productivity implied by holistic sustainable system, less depending chem-based approaches upon a synthetic and chemical fertilizers with controlled application for natural healing factors that traces organic elements moving in their biological condition right through baking process.

Role of microflora in soil health

Microbial actions in the soil play a very critical role to the entire ecosystem of terrestrial. However, there is an equally important role of microflora in mineral cycling in the soil. For instance, symbiotic nitrogen-fixing bacteria such as Rhizobium and Azotoscapers change the atmospheric nitrogen into usable form for plants that promote plant growth as well as increase soil fertility (Mahmud et al., 2015). Decomposition of complex phosphorus compounds to the readily available plant-useful form is one very important factor which requires mention in this regard as it involves phosphate- solubilizing microorganisms like mycorrhizal fungi.

The microflora also perform an essential part in organic matter, which makes humus the organic compound of soil. As a result, the degradation ensures that required nutrients are released into the soil and make an appropriate environment for plants (Kögel-Knabner et al., 2010). In addition, microorganisms decompose the plant residues which in turn close the loop of nutrients and also aid in soil structure. Microflora of the soil is an integral part of the functioning terrestrial ecosystems, because microorganisms play a critical role in the processes of nutrient cycling, decomposition of organic matter and overall fertility (Richardson et al., 2009).

1. Nutrient Cycling:

Microorganisms, like Rhizobium, Azotobacter, are main contributors of nutrient cycling. They transform the nitrogen present in atmosphere into plant-available forms, encouraging plant-growth and enhancing fertility of the soil (Bhattacharyya et al. 2015).

2. Phosphorus Solubilization:

Phosphate-solubilizing microorganisms like mycorrhizal fungi are very essential for the phosphorus degradation complexing compounds which enhances the availability of phosphorus to plants and also enhances fertility of the soil (Richardson et al. 2009).

3. Soil Structure and Stability:

The microbial secretions like polysaccharides facilitate soil aggregation thereby improving soil structure and stability. This in turn improves the retention, water infiltration, also erosion and compaction resistance (Six et al. 2004).

4. Plant-Microbe Interactions:

Beneficial microbes form various symbiotic relationships with plants, as nodules or mycorrhizal associations. Such interactions enhance the nutrient absorption and overall plant performance, resulting in the ability of plants to endure environmental stresses (Smith et al. 2011). Understanding and appreciating the multifaceted contributions of microflora in soil health are essential for implementing sustainable soil management practices.

Impact on nutrient cycling and plant growth

Many beneficial microorganisms have a tremendous influence on nutrient cycling and hence plant growth, an integral component to sustain fertility of soil and ensure food productivity. Nitrogen-fixing bacteria, Rhizobium and Azotobacter among others are of critical importance in nutrient cycling since they convert atmospheric nitrogen into plant available forms. The nitrogen fixation depiction increases soil nitrogen succumbing to the growths and nursery diminishing the expectation for made utilizations of rationale nitrogen sustenances (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015). The introduction of these bacteria in the soils has a positive effect on nutrient cycles dynamics. Mycorrhizal fungi are involved in processes of nutrient cycling because they form mutualistic relationship with the roots of plants. These are fungi, which elongate the roots of the plants and increase their capacity for absorbing nutrients especially phosphorus. The effect serves to enhance the quality of nutrient-use efficiency and encourage plant wellness that works to improve nutrient cycling in soils (Richardson et al., 2009).

Further, the phosphate-solubilizing bacteria i.e., Bacillus and Pseudomonas play a very important role in making phosphorus available to plants. These bacteria play a significant role in the nutrient cycle and also plant nutrition by their function of solubilizing insoluble phosphates from soil, which are making roots strong for plant growth. The application of these beneficial microbes in the agricultural environment through the use of biofertilizers leads not only to improved nutrient cycling but also promotes sustainable plant growth.

Types of Biofertilizers

Biofertilizers are of several types, each serving different purposes in improving soil fertility and encouraging plant growth due to introduction of the beneficial microorganisms. The main types comprise of nitrogen-fixing biofertilizers, phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizers, and potassium-mobilizing biofertilizers.

Nitrogen-fixing Biofertilizers:

Nitrogen-fixing bacteria, such as Rhizobium, Azotobacter, and Azospirillum, are crucial components of nitrogen-fixing biofertilizers. These bacteria establish symbiotic relationships with plants or reside in the soil, converting atmospheric nitrogen into a form that plants can readily use, thereby augmenting soil nitrogen levels and supporting plant growth (Gyaneshwar et al., 2002).

Phosphate-solubilizing Biofertilizers:

Mycorrhizal fungi and certain bacterial species, such as Bacillus and Pseudomonas, fall under the category of phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizers. These microorganisms play a vital role in breaking down insoluble phosphates in the soil, enhancing phosphorus availability to plants and promoting improved root development (Richardson et al., 2009).

Potassium-mobilizing Biofertilizers:

Some bacteria such as *B. mucilaginosus* are classified as the potassium-mobilizing biofertilizers. These bacteria promote the potassium extraction from mineral sources in the soil, making that nutrient much more available to the plants. This leads to enhanced nutritional uptake and the general plant health.

The various types of biofertilizers provide many unique benefits in combating the nutrient deficiencies and fostering overall sustainability within the agricultural operations.

Distinction from chemical fertilizers

The distinction between biofertilizers and chemical fertilizers lies in their composition, mode of action, and environmental impact. Unlike chemical fertilizers, which are manufactured from synthetic compounds, biofertilizers consist of living microorganisms or natural substances that enhance nutrient availability through biological processes (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015).

Composition:

Chemical Fertilizers: Composed of synthetic compounds, chemical fertilizers typically contain concentrated forms of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) in specific ratios.

Biofertilizers: Comprise living microorganisms such as nitrogen-fixing bacteria, phosphate-solubilizing bacteria or fungi, and other beneficial microbes. They may also include organic materials that promote microbial activity in the soil.

Mode of Action:

Chemical Fertilizers: Act as direct nutrient sources for plants, providing readily available forms of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium.

Biofertilizers: Work indirectly by enhancing nutrient availability through biological processes. For example, nitrogen-fixing bacteria convert atmospheric nitrogen into plant-usable forms, and phosphate-solubilizing microorganisms break down insoluble phosphates in the soil.

Environmental Impact:

Chemical Fertilizers: Can contribute to environmental issues, such as nutrient runoff leading to water pollution, soil degradation, and greenhouse gas emissions during production.

Biofertilizers: Generally, have lower environmental impacts. They promote sustainable agricultural practices by reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers, minimizing nutrient runoff, and fostering healthier soil ecosystems (Glick, 2012).

Sustainability:

Chemical Fertilizers: Often associated with concerns related to long-term soil health, environmental pollution, and dependence on non-renewable resources.

Biofertilizers: Contribute to sustainable agriculture by promoting natural nutrient cycling, reducing reliance on synthetic inputs, and enhancing overall soil fertility (Gyaneshwar et al., 2002).

Examples of biofertilizers

Examples of biofertilizers include Rhizobium, Azotobacter, and Azospirillum, each playing a crucial role in enhancing soil fertility and promoting plant growth through unique mechanisms.

Nitrogen-fixing biofertilizers

Rhizobium:

Symbiotic Nitrogen Fixation: Rhizobium bacteria have symbiotic associations with plants that belong to the Fabaceae family, which includes legumes such as peas and beans, as well as white clover. Rhizobium is used within specialized root nodules to convert atmospheric nitrogen to ammonium, a usable form for the plant's growth. This process not only adds nitrogen into the soil but also helps in getting better plant growth (Gyaneshwar et al., 2002).

Azotobacter:

Free-living Nitrogen Fixation: Azotobacter is an autonomous bacteria that fixes the nitrogen from atmosphere. The process enables soil fertility to be improved because atmospheric nitrogen is fixed into ammonia and hence available for use by the plant. The enhancement of plant nutrition and soil health is a consequence of Azotobacter colonisation in various environmental conditions, which promotes nitrogen availability.

Azospirillum:

Plant Growth Promotion: It is reported that Azospirillum can enhance the effective growth of plants because it helps in absorbing nutrients. It also improves synthesis of plant growth regulators such as auxins while enhancing soil phosphates solubility. This then results in much better rooting, absorption of nutrients and plant strength. In addition, Azospirillum is particularly effective for non-legumes like cereals and grasses according to Dobbelaere et al (2001).

Mechanism of Nitrogen fixation:

Nitrogen fixation, a very important process in which atmospheric nitrogen is converted into a useable form by the plants however is mainly done through certain microorganisms of them; most effective being nitrogen-fixing bacteria. There are complicated biochemical processes that take place among these bacteria to facilitate nitrogen fixation.

Enzymatic Action:

Nitrogen fixation is made possible by the enzyme nitrogenase which exists in all bacteria that have its ability to fix nitrogen such as Rhizobium. The enzyme converts the atmospheric nitrogen (N_2) to ammonia (NH_3), which is a usable form of N by plants (Gyaneshwar et al. 2002).

Symbiotic Associations:

Legumes are common targets for nitrogen-fixing bacteria, with the two engaging in symbiosis. For instance, Rhizobium produces nodules on the roots of plants undergoing leguminous. Inside these nodules, these bacteria carry out nitrogen fixation from the atmosphere and benefit both them and their host plants through the release of ammonia (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015).

The mechanism of nitrogen fixation is represented in fig 1, below; Knowledge on these mechanisms are essential in utilizing the nitrogen-fixing bacteria for agricultural purposes. Through the encouraging symbiotic relationships or using free-living nitrogen fixing bacteria farmers can increase nutrient accessibility in soil, minimize their chemical fertilizer reliance, and support sustainable farming practices.

Phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizers

The Biofertilizers, which are capable of phosphate solubility play the important role in increasing fertility of soil by giving access to plant's phosphorus. It is these microorganisms such as some bacteria and fungi that use mechanisms for solubilization of insoluble phosphates in the soil, which lead to better phosphorus uptake by plants.

Mycorrhizal Fungi:

Mycorrhizal fungi have a mutualistic relationship with plant roots; they increase the range of nutrient absorption among plants especially phosphorus. These microscopic fungus produce organic acids and enzymes which tackle complex phosphates to simpler, soluble forms hence making more availability of phosphorus required by the plant (Richardson et al., 2009).

Phosphate-solubilizing Bacteria:

Some common phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizers are Bacterial species of Bacillus and Pseudomonas. These bacteria produce organic acids which include gluconic and citric acids, that dissolve insoluble phosphates in the soil. Moreover, phosphate-solubilizing bacteria also

secrete phosphatase enzymes that help in solubilization of the element (Vyas et al., 2009).

Plant Growth-promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR):

Some PGPR strains, including phosphate-solubilizing bacteria increase the availability of phosphorus in soils and promote plant growth by mechanisms that include the production of hormones and siderophores which facilitate nutritional uptake.

The presence of these micro-organisms helps to increase phosphorus availability in the soil, lowering the need for chemical fertilizers containing phosphorus and thereby reducing pollution through runoff.

Examples

Some of the phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizers include mycorrhizae and phosphobacteria, both being effective in improving the availability of phosphorus and plant vigor.

Mycorrhizae:

Mycorrhizal fungi are symbionts of plant root systems, producing mycorrhizae structures. Solubilizing phosphorus is done by these fungi in significant amount after releasing organic acids and enzymes which break down insoluble phosphates in the soil. The mycorrhizal network increases the roots of the plant, improving nutrient absorption, especially phosphorus availability and benefits plant health (Richardson et al., 2009).

Fig. 1 Mechanism of Nitrogen fixation and promotion of plant growth by the use of biofertilizers [Zeenat et al, 2021].

Phosphobacteria:

They are represented by Phosphobacteria, which include strains of Bacillus and Pseudomonas. These bacteria also secrete organic acids like gluconic and citric acids that effectively solubilize insoluble phosphates in the soil. Phosphobacteria not only contribute towards phosphorus solubilization but also act as plant growth promoter making them important biofertilizer for sustainable agriculture (Vyas et al., 2009).

Role in phosphorous availability

Phosphobacteria and Mycorrhizae play a crucial part in improving availability of phosphorus in the soil, contributing to enhanced plant nutrition and agricultural productivity. Mycorrhizal fungi form cooperative relations with plant roots, releasing enzymes and organic-acids that break-down insoluble phosphates, making phosphorus more manageable to plants (Richardson et al. 2009). This mycorrhizal network encompasses the effective root surface area, improving phosphorus uptake efficiency. Phosphobacteria, including Pseudomonas and Bacillus strains, solubilize insoluble phosphates via the production of organic acids like gluconic and citric acids, releasing plant-available phosphorus (Vyas et al. 2009). By facilitating the conversion of phosphates into usable forms, both phosphobacteria and mycorrhizae contribute to sustainable agriculture, reducing the need for chemical fertilizers.

Potassium-mobilizing biofertilizers

Potassium-mobilizing biofertilizers are vital machineries in sustainable agriculture, contributing to enhanced availability of potassium for plants and improving soil fertility. Certain bacteria, like Bacillus mucilaginosus, illustrate potassium-mobilizing biofertilizers.

1. Bacillus mucilaginosus:

Bacillus mucilaginosus is known for its capability to mobilize potassium in the soil. This bacterium produces natural acids and exopolysaccharides that aid inside the solubilization of fixed potassium, making it greater available to plant roots (Kucey, 1983).

Potassium Mobilization: Bacillus mucilaginosus is known for its capability to solubilize fixed potassium within the soil. This bacterium secretes exopolysaccharides and organic acids, creating an

environment for the release of potassium from mineral sources (Kucey, 1983).

Improved Nutrient Availability: By easing the mobilization of potassium, Bacillus mucilaginosus balances nutrient availability in the soil. This, in turn, helps better potassium uptake with the aid of plant roots, contributing to progressed plant growth and typical crop yield.

Sustainable Agriculture: The software of Bacillus mucilaginosus as a biofertilizer represents a sustainable method to potassium-control in agriculture. It reduces the need for excessive potassium fertilization, encouraging resource efficiency and diminishing the environmental impact related to potassium runoff. Integrating Bacillus mucilaginosus into agricultural practices exemplifies the capability of potassium-mobilizing biofertilizers to promote sustainable farming, beautify nutrient utilization and make a contribution to the overall wellness of agricultural ecosystems.

Potassium mobilization mechanisms

The potassium mobilization mechanisms by biofertilizers including Bacillus mucilaginosus are complex biochemical processes that increase the auspicious fixation of potassium on soil which therefore improves plant uptake as well. Bacillus mucilaginosus uses several important mechanisms in the process of potassium mobilization.

Secondly, this bacterium's organic acids help solubilize potassium from mineral sources within the soil such as citric acid and oxalic acid (Kucey, 1983). Organic acids emitted by Bacillus mucilaginosus serve as chelating agents that create complexes with the fixed potassium and make it more soluble and available to plants roots. Second, Bacillus mucilaginosus releases exopolysaccharides that aid in soil structure improvement and enhance the cation exchange capacity. This increases the retention and mobility of potassium in the soil, creating a microenvironment suitable for optimal functional uptake by plant roots. The mechanism is depicted pictorially in fig 2, below;

Fig. 2 Mechanism of Potassium mobilization and promotion of plant growth by the use of potassium-mobilizing biofertilizers [Bakshandeh et al, 2017].

Advantages of Biofertilizers

i) Enhanced Soil structure:

Biofertilizers play an important role in ensuring a better soil structure, which creates conducive surroundings for plant growth as well as the overall health of the soil. The soil aggregation is facilitated by the secretion of microbial metabolites such as exopolysaccharides and organic acids by biofertilizer microorganisms as reported by Six et al. (2004). These compounds function as binders that stabilize the aggregates, resulting in improved soil structure. As a part of the biofertilizer applications, mycorrhizal fungi further enhance soil structure through hyphae network, which creates stable and resistant matrix (Smith, 2011). Increased soil structure promotes water infiltration, reduces erosion and supply the roots of plants with adequate oxygen. Moreover, it assists in micronutrient retention and promotes root growth.

ii) Enhanced nutrient availability

The advantages of biofertilizers in sustainable agriculture are many. To begin with, they increase nutrient availability in the soil by nitrogen fixation, phosphates solubilization and potassium mobilization. Additionally, biofertilizers are associated with positive soil health due to development of beneficial microorganisms, building up the structure of soil and minimizing reliance on chemical fertilizers. Thirdly, such eco-friendly alternatives help in assuring environmental sustainability through the reduction of nutrient runoffs and greenhouse gases that result from use of synthetic fertilizers. Moreover, biofertilizers improve plant growth, yield and the general ability of crops to withstand stress. Their use provides a continuous nutrient supply to plants and helps to maintain soil fertility in the long-run, thus making them important allies of sustainable farm practices.

iii) Yield promotion and plant growth

Biofertilizers are vital in facilitating plant growth and increasing crop production using several ways. Rhizobium and Azotobacter are among the bacteria that fix nitrogen; they contribute to improved plant growth by enabling transformation of atmospheric nitrogen into a form usable by plants, resulting in vigorous vegetative development (Gyaneshwar et al., 2002). Application of the phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizers such as mycorrhizal fungi and phosphate-solubilizing bacteria increase uptake of nutrients, plant root growth, and overall productivity leading to increased crop yields (Richardson et al., 2009; Vyas et al., 2009).

The collective influence of phosphorus solubilization, nitrogen fixation and potassium mobilization by biofertilizers synergistically augments plant-growth, leading to improved crop-yields, making them valuable components of high-yielding, sustainable agricultural systems.

iv) Reduction of environmental impact

Biofertilizers contribute to the decrease in environmental-impact in agriculture, addressing concerns related to greenhouse gas emissions and pollution. These are elaborated as:

a. Decreased Pollution:

The use of biofertilizers reduces the reliance on synthetic fertilizers, minimizing the risk of nutrient runoff into water bodies. Synthetic fertilizers can contribute to water pollution by carrying excess nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, into rivers and lakes, leading to issues like eutrophication. Biofertilizers, being derived from living organisms and promoting natural nutrient cycling, mitigate these pollution risks, ensuring a more sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural approach (Glick, 2012).

b. Lower Greenhouse Gas Emissions:

Biofertilizers, by enhancing nutrient-use efficiency and reducing the need for chemical fertilizers, contribute to lower greenhouse gas emissions associated with fertilizer production and application. The manufacturing and application of synthetic fertilizers involve energy-intensive processes and can release greenhouse gases like nitrous oxide. Utilizing biofertilizers helps in minimizing these emissions, aligning with the goals of sustainable and climate-friendly agricultural practices (Gyaneshwar et al., 2002).

Limitations and challenges of biofertilizers

Biofertilizers, while contributing numerous benefits, face several limitations and challenges that disturb their widespread adoption in agriculture.

Shelf life and viability:

A problem associated with biofertilizers is that they contain living micro-organisms, which means that their shelf life and viability are of particular concern. Environmental factors like temperature, humidity and storage conditions can alter the effective lifespan of beneficial microorganisms (Kloepper et al., 1980). Conserving the viability of biofertilizers in the field until they are applied is essential to their success as a fertilizer.

Compatibility with other agricultural inputs:

It is a challenge to produce biofertilizers which are compatible with chemical fertilizers and pesticides, as the use of some chemicals can hamper their survival and performance. However, locating the appropriate balance and creating formulations that are workable with a range of agricultural inputs is critical to their successful implementation as part of regular farming practices (Glick, 2012).

Awareness and adoption by farmers:

A serious challenge to the use of biofertilizers lies in the fact that farmers are only poorly aware and knowledgeable on their advantages as well as their usage. The main strategy to increase the acceptance of farmers that should be adopted is public awareness, education concerning biofertilizers, and proving success examples of them (Nosheen et al., 2021).

Economic considerations:

Some of these limitations can be costs associated with production of biofertilizers. The costs of production and adoption by farmers may be higher than that for conventional fertilizers (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015).

It is necessary to study and develop formulations to respond to these challenges in order for biofertilizers to realize their potential as sustainable solutions in the contemporary agricultural practice.

Case Studies

Case Study on successful implementation of biofertilizers:

1. Application of Azospirillum in Rice Cultivation- China:

The introduction of Azospirillum-based biofertilizers into the rice cultivation system has also revealed positive results in China. Since the Azospirillum inoculation was introduced by farmers in Zhejiang province, it also meant better yield of nitrogen fixation and paddy. The usage of the biofertilizer application allowed sustainable rice production and also demonstrated its potential to low dependence on synthetic nitrogen fertilizers' (Liang et al., 2017).

2. Inoculation of Rhizobium in Legume Cropping Systems- Kenya:

The Rhizobium inoculation practice was a success story that was highlighted by a case study conducted in Kenya on the efficacy of inoculation trials. In this region farmers adopted Rhizobium strains and used them in the field to cultivate leguminous crops such as peas and beans. Biofertilizer application resulted in better nitrogen fixation, soil fertility improvement and greater legume yields without the use of mineral fertilizers that are unaffordable to smallholder farmers (Njeru et al. 2019).

These case studies show that biofertilizers are flexible and effective across various agroecological setups, highlighting their role in sustainable agriculture and disseminating specific regional best practices.

b) Case Study on impact on crop yield and soil health:

1. Nitrogen-Fixing Bacteria in Sugarcane Plantations- Brazil:

In Brazil, the case study centered on the use of bacteria that fix nitrogen as a form of organic fertilizer— biofertilizers- in sugarcane plantations. The inoculation of nitrogen-fixing bacteria resulted to increased nitrogen fixation, higher productivity, more fertile soils and high sugarcane harvests. The study focused on the potential of biofertilizers and their impact in achieving sustainable sugarcane production, which will minimize the use of synthetic nitrogen fertilizer and reduce environmental pollution (Boddey et al. 2003).

2. Phosphate-Solubilizing Bacteria in Chickpea Farming- India:

In the Deccan Plateau of India, a research study investigated how chickpeas respond to PSB application. PSB biofertilizers that were introduced improved soil phosphorus availability, and consequently the chickpea plants took more nutrients from the ground where a considerable increment in production was realized. The trial on phosphorus-deficient soils showed the potential for use of PSB to overcome issues associated with lack of phosphorus in nutrient-deficient soils (Goswami et al., 2016).

These case studies reveal the beneficial effects of biofertilizers not only on crop yields but also soil quality proving successful application under various geographical and agricultural conditions.

c) On Lessons learned and best practices:

1. Integrated Biofertilizer adoption in Rice Farming-Vietnam:

The case study of biofertilizers was adopted in the Mekong Delta region of Vietnam which focused on integrated biofertilizer adoption in rice-based farming systems. The farmers used biofertilizers with nitrogen-fixation to combine the organic amendments, which demonstrated a synergistic effect on nutrient availability. The integrated approach resulted in higher yields of rice, crop independence on chemical fertilizers, and better soil. This case study emphasizes the need to integrate biofertilizers with organic procedures to achieve balanced and whole nutrient regulation through sustainable means (Linh et al., 2015).

2. Scaling up Legume inoculation practices- Ethiopia:

A research study conducted in Ethiopia was available on scaling up legume inoculation practices with the use of Rhizobium biofertilizers. There is also the adoption of legume inoculants along with awareness campaigns which showed considerable increases in legume yields and soil fertility. From this case study, some of the lessons learnt notable include community engagement, extension services and platforms for knowledge sharing were critical and key in undertaking biofertilizer technologies at a larger scale (Sanginga, 2003).

These case studies allow us to learn lessons and adopt the best biofertilizer practices for successful adoption, highlighting integrated approaches, farmer education, community engagement.

Future Perspectives

a) Research and development in biofertilizers:

The development of biofertilizers is accurately considered to be directly linked to ongoing research and development efforts designed towards enhancing their efficiency, increasing microbial variety and tailoring formulations based on growing needs in agriculture. Developments in comprehending microbe-microbe interactions, genome analysis and plant microbiome are key to improve biofertilizer effectiveness. For example, it is revealed by Bhattacharyya et al. (2015) that persistent researches on isolating and defining new strains with better nutrient-fixing capacity can result in strong and efficient biofertilizers.

Additionally, the synergistic use of advanced technologies, such as metagenomics and synthetic biology, enables scientists to engineer microbial communities for better nutrient recycling and plant-microbe interactions (Vorholt et al., 2017). This multi-disciplinary approach helps in improving biofertilizer formulation that is more suited to disparate agroecosystems. More research also seeks to reveal the complex signaling network between plants and beneficial microbes, which may eventually translate into applications for precision agriculture strategies (Zhang et al., 2018). Precision agriculture, due to its data-driven and technology-intensive nature, can enhance the usage of biofertilizers so that nutrients are delivered more specifically to the crops. The plot in Fig 3, depicts the yearly growth of the biofertilizer production in India from 1992 onwards:

b) Integration with precision agriculture:

The incorporation of biofertilizers into precision agriculture is a novel strategy that aims at minimizing the use and maximizing the efficiency in nutrient management on crop production. For precision agriculture, which adopts data-driven decisions and has implemented technology adoption involves a platform on the biofertilizer applications efficiency. Zhang et al. (2018) hint at the possible synergy of precision agriculture and biofertilizers, where technology takes on a crucial function in delivering nutrients to crops. There is no doubt that precision agriculture technologies, like GPS guided equipment and remote sensing allow specific soil mapping of the variability to align biofertilizer applications based on nutritional needs across the field. This site-specific application approach not only promotes effective use of biofertilizers but also helps to limit over fertilization which helps in minimizing environmental impact. Integration with precision agriculture also encompasses real-time monitoring of crop wellness and soil parameters. Integration of advanced sensor technologies and data analytics enables farmers to use biofertilizers judiciously, with the dosage based on the environmental condition in each crop field. This type of approach is

dynamic and adaptive, which makes precision agriculture principles to be observed – with biofertilizers being applied where and when they are needed most. Fig 4, below shows the consumption of different biofertilizers in India in comparison to the major biofertilizers consuming parts of the world.

c) Role in food security and sustainable agriculture:

Biofertilizers are crucial in the future role of sustainable agriculture and food security. Along with the issues that global agriculture is facing such as climate changes and limitations on resources, biofertilizers are an environmentally friendly alternative. Biofertilizers are making noteworthy contributions in supporting sustainable agriculture, and ensuring food security on a global scale. However, the sustainable use of biofertilizers is in line with eco-friendly and resourced saving agriculture. Biofertilizers play a role in promoting biological processes like nitrogen fixation, phosphorus solubilization, and potassium mobilization which enhance

availability of nutrients from the soil (Glick, 2012). This in turn ensures better plant vigor, production and eventual crop adaptability. It is the environmental advantages of biofertilizers that the reliance on synthetic fertilizers will be reduced as well as lowering the impacts since nutrients are deposited into water bodies. Moreover, the microbial activity promoted by biofertilizers improves soil structure, water storage, and nutrient cycling leading to long-term sustainability of soils (Lehman et al., 2012).

Biofertilizers provide a sustainable and environment-friendly solution to boost production in terms of food security. The adoption of these technologies helps to support smallholder farmers by giving them cheaper options as compared to chemical fertilizers thereby reducing production costs and improving economic returns. In addition, biofertilizers contribute to the increase in nutrient sources' diversity that help decrease dependence on non-renewable mineral resources and support resilient and sustainable agriculture systems.

Fig 3 Growth in carrier-based solid biofertilizer production in India from 1992–93 to 2020–21.

[Source: Biofertilizer Statistics 2019–20 (12th edition), the Fertilizer Association of India, December 2020; Lok Sabha unstarred question 413, pesticides and biofertilizers, 30 November 2021, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare; Lok Sabha unstarred question 2,549, 1 August 2017; biofertilizer production, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare, Govt. of India].

Fig 4. Pie charts showing the consumption of biofertilizers by India and other parts of the world [Randive, et al, 2021]. Overall biofertilizers's significance in sustaining fertility and soil microflora

In context of sustainable agriculture and soil health over a long time period, the importance of biofertilizers in sustaining the performance of microflora as well as fertility is crucial. Biofertilizers, through their relations with plants and soil microorganisms, contribute to numerous key aspects that are influential for maintaining soil fertility:

Microbial Activity and Diversity: Biofertilizers including nitrogen-fixing bacteria and mycorrhizal fungi enhance soil microbial activity and diversity. Nevertheless, these positive microbes develop synergistic relationships with plants leading to a well-functioning microbial community that ultimately conditions organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling (Lehmann et al., 2012).

Soil structure Improvement: Biofertilizers also contribute to better soil-structure due to the production of exopolysaccharides and other compounds. This enhanced soil aggregation supports better water holding capacity, root development and increased aeration; leading to a suitable condition for plant growth and microbial activities (Smith & Read 2008).

Nutrient Availability and Cycling: The biological activities of biofertilizers lead to the enhanced availability of essential nutrients, including phosphorus, nitrogen and potassium in soil. Nitrogen-fixing bacteria facilitate the conversion of atmospheric nitrogen into a plant-available form, and phosphate solubilizing microorganisms enhance phosphorus availability. This nutrient cycling guarantees a homogeneous and constant source of nutrients for plant absorption (Glick, 2012).

Reduction of Environmental Impact: Through elimination of the use of chemical fertilizers, biofertilizers help to avoid the negative environmental effects associated with nutrient run off and pollution. This environmentally friendly approach is consistent with the principles of sustainable agriculture, reducing the impact on water bodies and ecosystems (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015).

Promotion of Sustainable Agriculture: The incorporation of biofertilizers into farming systems contributes to the ideals of sustainable agriculture. Their use leads to lower levels of synthetic input dependence, improved soil durability and sustainable environmental management. The sustainable mechanization approach ensures that the agricultural ecosystems are productive and healthy for a long period (Hungria et al., 2006).

Call to action for augmented adoption in agriculture

The compelling benefits of biofertilizers in promoting sustainable agriculture and enhancing soil fertility necessitate a collective call to action for increased adoption. To realize the full potential of biofertilizers, stakeholders at various levels—farmers, policymakers, researchers, and industry players—need to collaborate and prioritize their integration into mainstream agricultural practices.

Farmers play a central role in this call to action. Awareness programs and educational initiatives should be intensified to inform farmers about the benefits of biofertilizers, their proper application methods, and the positive impacts on crop yields and soil health (Witt et al., 2012). Providing access to high-quality, locally adapted biofertilizer formulations can incentivize adoption, especially among smallholder farmers.

Policymakers should consider implementing supportive policies, including incentives or subsidies, to encourage the use of biofertilizers. Incorporating biofertilizers into agricultural extension services and certification programs can further facilitate their widespread adoption.

Researchers need to continue advancing the science behind biofertilizers, addressing challenges such as shelf life, compatibility with other inputs, and economic considerations. Ongoing research and development efforts will contribute to improving the efficacy and versatility of biofertilizers, making them more attractive to farmers and stakeholders (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015).

By actively engaging farmers, policymakers, and researchers, we can collectively harness the potential of biofertilizers, paving the way for sustainable agriculture, enhanced soil fertility, and global food security.

Conclusion

In summary, the review paper stresses biochemical significance of biofertilizers in promoting sustainable agriculture, enhancing soil fertility and contributing to global food sufficiency. The important outcomes reveal different ways of biofertilizers work—nitrogen fixation, phosphorus solubilization and potassium mobilisation in the soil making nutrient availability better. Building symbiotic connections between plants and biofertilizers develops microbial diversity leading to a highly dynamic and stable soil ecosystem. Biofertilizers, especially in terms of their environmental implications and specifically the reduction of pollution risks deriving from chemical fertilizers, thus are an important tool for eco-friendly farming. Recognizing difficulties as well as restrictions, which include the shelf life and also economic aspects, the review offers solutions and points out lessons learnt from successful cases that should be taken into account during further research and practice. In the future, available prospective perspectives highlight the emergence of tailor made formulation for biofertilizer used in certain crops and agroecological environments. The use of biofertilizers as part and parcel of the precision agriculture is regarded as a new era in agricultural practices, embracing technology-intensive farming methods and improving utilization of biofertilizer solutions on the farm. The call to action asks farmers, policymakers and researchers to make concerted efforts in helping the what biofertilizers through increased adoption. In conclusion, some of the recommendations encompass sensitization programs, educational projects and policies aimed at ensuring support for integration on a wide scope. Thus, biofertilizers embraced as part and parcel of sustainable agriculture enable stakeholders to participate in resilient agricultural systems upholding fertile soils that lead to food security.

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